

Promising Practices - Several Plein-air Societies Hold Hands to Embrace Coexistence

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On the one hand, Covid-19 brought sadness and depression; on the other hand, the virus is a wake-up call to serve a minute for ourselves and the people around us; it's high time to re-examine ourselves. The International Council of Museum (ICOM) redefine the museum definition as not merely researching, collecting, conserving, interpreting and exhibiting the tangible and the intangible elements; it should encourage the community to be involved in all layers of participation thru education, enjoyment, reflection and knowledge sharing. Evoking coexistence sentiment or showing concern for people around us is the new norm practised to live with Covid-19 around the globe.

Asia Network Beyond Design (ANBD) 2022 Phuket Special Exhibition react to the impact of the post-pandemic, themed Coexistence as the subject of discussion through design. 2022 The 19th Busan International Design Festival (BIDF) also responded to the post-pandemic and promoted living with Covid-19; in other words, the 2022 BIDF also encourages Coexistence. Museum and Gallery Tuanku Fauziah (MGTF), USM, already championed experiential learning to enhance the viewing experience of their museum exhibits. In local practices, before the pandemic, MGTF has constantly engaged with the community, encouraging visitors to play, touch, feel, listen, and interact physically, shifting from the older observation method of the cabinet of curiosity.

MGTF has expanded the practice of experiential learning. The institution invites visitors to view and encourages them to co-curate, act as contributors to the displays, and imagine the MGTF as a knowledge playground to join, opine, share, and make marks in several exhibitions - "Open Wall", "Project Monyet", "OYEN: A Story about B.E.L.A.S." Those are excellent examples of embracing the notion of Coexistence.

The Penang State Art Gallery (PSAG) also captured the wave of change. It shifted into the engagement to involve the artist community in their curatorial practices and involved in educational events in selected exhibitions, namely "MERGASTUA: Taxidermy = Art + Science Combined. ", "Pameran Seni Lukis LangUR", "Talking Object; Seeing Through Young Eyes", etc. and make PSAG won the Best Practice Award 2022 from ICOM International Committee for Education and Cultural Action (CECA).

Above are a few good examples of how institutions respond to the notion of Coexistence. The post-pandemic forced us to change our living and planted a new seed of shifting in the culture and art practices. We should ponder how the local art societies adapt to Coexistence in their practices.

The recent plein air program - Detik-detik Nostalgia Sg. Ujong was initiated by Negeri Sembilan State Museum, collaborating with Negeri Sembilan Art Society, embracing the spirit of Coexistence. The Negeri Sembilan Art Society invited several active plein air societies, such as Persatuan Pelukis Negeri Sembilan (PELUKIS), Sketchwalk Kuala Lumpur

(SKL), Klang Artists Society (KAS) and 180 Virtual Introverted Sketchers (180VIS) become their partners, and gather about 30 odds sketchers work collaboratively to capture, illustrate, imagine and conceptualise the selected historical sites; at Pengkalan Kempas (on 2 March 2023), Pekan Lama Nilai (on 16 March) and Pekan Lama Port Dickson (on 6 April 2023). The collaboration of 30 odds sketchers could be an excellent team to study the selected sites that may trace the early settlement of ancient traders from China, Minangkabau and other Western explorers. Hope this practice may expand the outcome of observation, not just restricted to the old buildings, but the trace of the texture on the wall, the people, the stories and even the daily practices; it may reflect the intangible elements and perhaps may capture the expression of the living heritage of the old towns. Again, this will encourage the sketchers to engage, conversate, and listen to the community, as another practice of Coexistence, or taking care of the people around us.

Stay tuned; the collaborative plein-air artworks will be exhibited at Negeri Sembilan Minangkabau State Museum from May to July 2023.

Thanks, SinChew reporter Khoo Teck Yong visited us on the field trip. And produce a comprehensive report on the Sin Chew Daily newspaper dated 19 March 2023.

Find out what the leaders opined?

1. Treasurer of Persatuan Pelukis Negeri Sembilan (PELUKIS), En Mazlan Bin Abu Bakar, believes that the artist's impression may enhance the interpretation of the nostalgia of the old town with a more truthful expression.
2. The President of Negeri Sembilan Art Society, Mr Yong Look Nam, embraced his adaptation of Coexistence and showed his open heart in inviting other art societies to be part of the event, sharing and exchanging opinions of in-situ observation study. He has a "big heart".
3. Secretary of Negeri Sembilan Art Society, Ms Foo Chee Hui, encourages sketchers to observe the building facade and structures, getting know the building's style, to interpret the building's history. And these may influence and impact someone's plein-air making.
4. The President of Klang Artists Society (KAS), Mr Lee Kee Seng, recalled that the friendship between both art societies may trace for more than 10 years. Negeri Sembilan State Museum has set a good role model to help local art practitioners; Lee hopes the Klang district authority may follow the act, supporting fellow art practitioners.
5. My statement as the leader of 180 Virtual Introverted Sketchers (180VIS) opined, seeing beyond the plein-air exercises and the visual manipulation; and attempting to learn about the history, observe the cultural appearance, feel the space of the architectural setting, and plan for the suitable mediums as the vessel to hold the impression of one's imagination.

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